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Parental Support, Self-Esteem And Emotional Intelligence As Predictors Of Social Anxiety Disorder Among Secondary School Students In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated parental support, self-esteem and emotional intelligence as predictors of social anxiety disorder among secondary school students in Rivers State. The design for the study is correlational research design. The population of the study consists of 4,982 SS3 students in public secondary schools in Rivers State with sample size of 370. Two adapted instruments were used for the study. The first is titled “Social Anxiety Disorder Scale (SADS) and the second titled “Parenting Support, Self-esteem and Emotional Intelligence Scale (PSSEIS). Research instruments were validated by the supervisor and two other experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation, from Department of Psychology, Guidance and Counselling University of Port Harcourt. Both Face and content validities of the instrument were done. The construct validity was also carried out using factor analysis. The significant value obtained ($0.000 < 0.005$) shows that the instrument is reasonably valid. Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to determine the following reliability coefficients as 0.79 for Social-Anxiety Disorder Scale (SADS), Parenting Support, Self-esteem and Emotional Intelligence Scale (PSSEIS) has 0.87, 0.77 and 0.69 for the three sections. Research questions were answered using simple regression. Hypotheses of this study were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) associated with simple regression at 0.05 level of significance with the use of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The study revealed that, the independent variables self-esteem and emotional intelligence (self-awareness, social awareness and self-management) significantly predicted the dependent variable (social anxiety disorder). It was recommended that in developing policies for schools, the Ministry of Education, School Administrators, Ministry of Women Affairs, Ministry of Youth Affairs, teachers and other stakeholders related to parental support on adolescents be given more serious consideration. Again, educators should pay more attention to the relationship between parental support and adolescents’ self-esteem. Furthermore, it was recommended that schools should provide functional counselling services to support the developmental and emotional growth of socially-anxious students, considering the fact that they often express fears and feelings of being negatively evaluated during events and in the classroom even when teaching and learning experience is going on and thereby lowering their sense of self-esteem.

Key words: Parental Support, Self-Esteem Emotional Intelligence and Social Anxiety Disorder

INTRODUCTION

The researcher being a priest had a personal experience with one of the students, a fellow seminarian during his seminary formation. Usually, assessments are done in written as well as oral form. On this fateful day, this my colleague who was to do his oral presentation on epistemology entered with me and three other students. As we individually picked ballots to speak on, the said student simply went dumb. When it was his turn, he was shaking like a leaf and sweating profusely. This was a rude shock to the researcher because the topic the student picked was same concept the said student discussed with him earlier that day. This became a worrisome case to the researcher because the said student was among the very brilliant ones that they all looked up to. One begins to wonder where the flaw emanated from. He was actually suffering from social anxiety disorder. Social anxiety disorder as social phobia is anxiety disorder characterized by sentiments of fear and anxiety in social situation, causing considerable distress and impaired ability to function in at least some aspects of daily life (National institute for Health and Clinical Excellence: Guidance, 2013). These fears can be triggered by perceived or actual scrutiny from others.

Social anxiety disorder is characterized by social situations that cause fear, avoidance, and anxiety. It entertains the fear of being judged, humiliated or embarrassed. It involves high level of stress in social situations and interferes in one's daily life, affecting the quality of life. Social anxiety is a prevalent disorder affecting the population, students in particular and it is currently a major psychological issue that affects many secondary students in Rivers State. In this study, the researcher will be surveying parental support, self-esteem and emotional intelligence as they relate to social anxiety disorder among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Social anxiety disorder is referred to as "the phobia or fear of interaction with other people that brings about self-consciousness, feelings of being judged negatively and evaluated, and, as such, leads to avoidance or low self-esteem" (Richards, 2012). Students with social anxiety disorder have an excessive and persistent fear of social and/or performance situations such as school, parties, athletic activities, and more. They are extremely worried that they may do something embarrassing, or others will think badly of them. These students constantly feel "on stage," which can lead to a great deal of self-consciousness, distress, and avoidance. Some students are only afraid of speaking or performing in public, while others fear and avoid a wide range of social situations. Looking closely at the symptoms of social anxiety disorder, one could perceive clearly that being a shy or quiet child is not the same as having social anxiety disorder. Considering anxiety regarding school setting and students, it is often defined as situational anxiety. Social anxiety disorder usually starts during late childhood, among adolescents and young adults, and may resemble extreme shyness or avoidance of situations or social interactions. It goes without the saying that these symptoms of social anxiety disorder, could be brought about by low self-esteem.

Furthermore, Self-esteem is a person's perception or belief in his own worth or value. It is one's subjective sense of overall personal worth or value. Similar to self-respect, it describes one's level of confidence in his or her abilities and attributes. It encompasses beliefs about oneself (for example, 'I am loved', I am worthy) as well as emotional states such as triumph, despair, pride and shame (Hewitt, 2009). According to Smith and Mackie (2007), self-esteem is the positive or negative evaluation of the self as in how one feels about it. It is an attractive psychological constructs that predicts certain outcomes.

Again, parental support is defined by Barnes in Essau and Hutchinson(2008) as parental behaviours towards the child, such as praising, encouraging and giving physical attention which indicate to the child that he or she is accepted and loved. Peer support may gain significance during the adolescence stage but parental support continues to weld its importance. According to Cohen in Tulia, In-Jae and Eunsoo (2020), parental support refers to parental provision of emotional and practical recourses to their adolescent children. It is a broad construct that comprises other kinds of support like emotional support (expressions of love, empathy, warmth and concern), informational support (information, guidance or counsel) and tangible support (material or financial assistance).Consequently, parental support is an essential component in the learning, growth, and development of children. What is more, the family is an

important source of recreation, relaxation and social interaction, especially in early childhood years. It is not out of place also, to think that parents with SAD may unknowingly perpetuate social anxiety.

Finally, Emotional intelligence (EI) is defined as the ability to perceive, use, understand, manage and handle emotions (Colman, 2008). People with high emotional intelligence can recognize their own emotions and those of others, use emotional information to guide thinking and behaviour, discern between feelings and label them appropriately and adjust emotions to adapt to environments. This ability to perceive, interpret, demonstrate, control, and use emotions to communicate with and relate to others effectively and constructively, is essential, but so is the ability to understand, interpret, and respond to the emotions of other people. Interest in teaching and learning social and emotional intelligence has grown in recent years. Social and emotional learning (SEL) programmes have become a standard part of the curriculum for many schools.

Theoretically, the study is anchored on Dynamic System Theory, Social Cognitive Theory by Albert Bandura in 1986 and Self-Awareness Theory by Wicklund in 1972, respectively. These theories delineate how parental support, self-esteem and emotional intelligence predict social anxiety among secondary school students. While, dynamic system theory is focused on studying a phenomenon that changes over time, the social cognitive theory emphasizes on behaviour, environment, and cognition as the key factors in development, and thus, self-awareness theory is concerned on the capacity to take oneself as the object of thought—people can think, act, and experience, and they can also think about what they are thinking, doing, and experiencing.

The prevailing social anxiety disorder among Secondary School Students and in the society at large, has given rise not only to low self-esteem and low emotional intelligence but also difficulties in speaking in the public, poor communication, low performance in oral examination, quizzes and debates. Lack of awareness of Social Anxiety Disorder on the part of the parents, resulting in poor parental support may not only heighten malady among secondary school students but may make the problem complex.

Moreover, students who are deficient in emotional intelligence will find it difficult to understand themselves and others. Hence, relationship mismanagement, quarrels, rancor and the likes becomes their behavioural patterns. The researcher having been opportune to teach in different secondary schools both seminary and public schools has observed with dismay the concurrence of social anxiety disorder among students of different intellectual abilities. It is against this backdrop that he decided to research on parental support, self-esteem and emotional intelligence as predictors of social anxiety disorder among secondary school students in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

Correlational research design was adopted for the study. the population of this study consists of four thousand nine hundred and eighty-two (4,982) SS3 students in public secondary schools in Rivers State.(Rivers State Ministry of Education, 2021/2022 academic session). Simple random sampling technique was used to sample 370 students from the population using Taro Yemen formula. Data were collected using two adapted instruments, the first instrument was titled “Social Anxiety Disorder Scale (SADS) and the second were titled “Parenting Support, Self-esteem and Emotional Intelligence Scale (PSSEIS). The instruments were validated by experts from measurement and evaluation, department of educational psychology and mathematics teachers in each of the schools. Construct validity of the instrument was determined through factor analysis. The factorial validity coefficient was determined under the condition that component correlational matrix loading was ($\geq .45$) and the Eigen values (>1) for each of the instruments. Cronbach Alpha method was used by the researcher for the determination of the reliability of the internal consistency of the instrument. Twenty (20) copies of the instruments were administered to SS3 students outside the study sample. Data gotten from this were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha statistics and reliability coefficient was determined as 0.79 for Social-Anxiety Disorder Scale (SADS). Parenting Support, Self-esteem and Emotional Intelligence Scale (PSSEIS) has 0.87, 0.77 and 0.69 for the three sections. Simple regression was used to answer the research questions while

ANOVA associated with simple regressions were used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance with the use of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study

1. To what extent does parental support predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does self-esteem predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does self-awareness of predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Parental support does not significantly predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State
2. Self-esteem does not significantly predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State
3. Self-awareness does not significantly predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *To what extent does parental support predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis One: Parental support does not significantly predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State

Table 2: Simple regression coefficient showing parental support as predictor of social anxiety disorder

R = 0.026	R² = 0.001			Adj R² = 0.102	
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	7.555	1	7.555	0.234	0.629
Residual	10876.610	337	32.275		
Total	10884.165	338			

According to the result shown in Table 2, a simple linear regression coefficient of 0.026 was obtained with a coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.001 and an adjusted coefficient (AdjR²) of 0.102 gotten when parental support was used to predict social anxiety disorder of students in secondary school students. From the result of the adjusted coefficient, it therefore implies that 10.2% variation of social anxiety disorder of secondary school students can be attributed to parenting support of the students. From the testing of the corresponding null hypothesis, it was indicated that an F-value of 0.234 was gotten at 1 and 337 degrees of freedom, with a corresponding p-value of 0.629. Since the p-value was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, this result therefore indicates that parental support does not significantly predict social anxiety disorder among secondary school students.

Research Question Two: *To what extent does self-esteem predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis Two: Self-esteem does not significantly predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State

Table 3: Simple regression coefficient showing the extent to which self-esteem predict social anxiety among secondary school students

R = 0.113	R² = 0.013			Adj R² = 0.010	
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	139.618	1	139.618	4.385	0.037
Residual	10729.804	337	31.839		
Total	10869.422	338			

Table 3 above reveals a simple linear regression coefficient of 0.113 which was obtained with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.013 and an adjusted coefficient ($AdjR^2$) of 0.010 gotten when self-esteem was used to predict social anxiety disorder of students in senior secondary school. From the result of the adjusted coefficient, it therefore implies that 1% variation of social anxiety disorder of secondary school students can be attributed to parenting support of the students.

From the testing of the corresponding null hypothesis, it was indicated that an F-value of 4.385 was gotten at 1 and 337 degrees of freedom, with a corresponding p-value of 0.037. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, this result therefore indicates that self-esteem significantly predict social anxiety among secondary school students.

Research Question Three: *To what extent does self-awareness predict social anxiety among econdary school students in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis Three: Self-awareness does not significantly predict social anxiety among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 3: Simple regression coefficient showing the extent to which self-awareness predict social anxiety among secondary school students

R = 0.045	R² = 0.0302			Adj R² = 0.350	
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	24.368	1	24.368	21.681	0.0006
Residual	12056.912	337	35.777		
Total	12081.280	338			

From the result of the analysis in table 3 above reveals a simple linear regression coefficient of 0.045 which was obtained with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.032 and an adjusted coefficient ($AdjR^2$) of 0.350 gotten when self-awareness predicts social anxiety disorder of students in senior secondary school. From the result of the adjusted coefficient, it therefore implies that 35% variation of social anxiety disorder of secondary school students can be attributed to self-awareness of the students.

From the testing of the corresponding null hypothesis, it was indicated that an F-value of 21.68 was gotten at 1 and 337 degrees of freedom, with a corresponding p-value of 0.0006. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected; this result therefore indicates that self-awareness significantly predicts social anxiety among secondary school students.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Parental support and social anxiety disorder among secondary school students

According to the result shown in Table 1 which implies indicates that parental support does not significantly predict social anxiety disorder among secondary school students. This finding is supported by Weiten (2007). He said academic anxiety is a kind of anxiety that can be learned, and it means that they can be “unlearned”. For instance, Parents frequently pass their worry to their children. Consequently, it is obvious that teachers, parents, and caretakers should be well informed and able to help academic anxious children to deal challenges. Meanwhile in order to raise learning efficiency, teachers should be stimulated to recognize conditions which may provoke child’s anxiety and try to make a suitable situation

for learning so that students during learning process can use and dedicate the considerable and large part of their working memory (Tummala-Narra, 2009). Teachers use of collaborative learning can raise student's learning and decrease their anxiety related to learning process, meanwhile teachers by keeping their classroom quiet and in hand raise the academic anxious student's attention and consideration and less be distracted by irrelevant things (Ioannou & Artino Jr, 2010). Studies in literature also show that there is a relationship between self-esteem and social anxiety. While social appearance anxiety was low in those with high self-esteem (Şirin, 2015; Kılıç, 2015), low self-esteem was seen in children who participated less in social events (ÇevikBüyükaşahinand, 2009). According to Sübaşı (2007), the most important predictors of social anxiety are the variables of self-esteem and loneliness. In many studies, self-esteem was negatively and significantly correlated with social anxiety (Kocovski and Endler, 2000; De Jong, 2002; Rasmussen & Pidgeon, 2011; De Jong, Sportel, De Hullu and Nauta, 2011).

On the other hand, there are few studies examining the three variables in the present study; self-esteem, parental attitudes and social anxiety. One of them, Eroglu (2018), found a negative correlation between social anxiety and self-esteem, and positive correlation with protective attitudes; and a positive relationship was determined between self-esteem and democratic attitudes.

Self-esteem and social anxiety disorder among secondary school students

Table 2 above reveals that self-esteem significantly predicts social anxiety disorder among secondary school students. This finding is supported by Sari et al. (2018) explained that one's self-esteem are considered to shape with lifelong learning experiences and dynamic processes that reflect one's unique perspective and traits. According to Jordan et al., (2017), self-esteem appears to be important to our mental and physical health. Studies have shown that it increases performance in specific areas, such as education, and has a good effect on our physical fitness and mental stability as well as social acceptance. According to Sadaat et al., (2012), as cited in the study of Arshad et al., (2015), academic and household self-esteem demonstrated a direct and positive link with student school related accomplishments at a significant. As mentioned in the study of Abdullah (2000) as cited in Arshad et al., (2015), regression analyses indicated that qualitative independent variables did not accurately predict an objective measure of student academic achievement. Sufficient psychology indicates that students' low motivation and self-esteem lead to a lack of desire in pursuing high academic achievement and a lack of passion for contributing positively and effectively to the country's development. According to the findings of Geel et al., (2018), individuals who experienced abuse by their peers has been shown to have long-term negative effects on self-esteem, but it's also possible that low self-esteem might result to individuals becoming victims. Busalim (2019), investigated the influence of abusive use of Facebook and self-esteem on student's accomplishments. According to the findings, students that abuse using Facebook are often to have lower self-esteem than to students who knows to use it properly. Thus, his findings provide empirical evidence of the influence of abusive usage of Facebook on school related achievement of students. Furthermore, his findings help to know more about the self-esteem factors that influence students' Facebook abusive usage and student's accomplishments.

Self-awareness of Emotional Intelligence and social anxiety disorder among secondary school students

From the result of the analysis in table 3 above indicates that self-awareness significantly predicts social anxiety disorder among secondary school students. The finding is supported by Lázaro, Moreno, Calvo, Vila, Andrés-Perpiñá & Castro-Fornieles (2011) the result showed that social skills and relationship have a relationship with self-esteem. The important outcomes showed that adolescents with a low level of social skills have a low level of self-esteem. Mota & Matos (2013) studied self-esteem and social skills. The result showed that adolescents with a high level of self-esteem have a better and higher level of social skills, relationships with peers, and their partner. Also, Xin & Liu (2019) had studied adolescent self-esteem and social adaption in China, the result shows that self-esteem can be affected by social adaption and it (self-esteem) can be mediated by peer trust and perceived social support. Danneel, Colpin, Goossens, Engels, Leeuwen, Noortgate & Verschuere (2019) the results show that only the negative experience of peer rejection plays an important role in emotional school engagement and self-esteem of

adolescents. In the same year, the study by Bala, Sangwan & Rani (2019) showed that self-esteem and social esteem can affect each other. The result of this study showed that one of the important items for social skills is self-esteem.

CONCLUSION

This study clearly shows that parental support is a key element in the parent child relationship. When parents support their children's basic psychological need for autonomy, competence and relatedness, such support in the familial context is associated with a host of positive child outcomes. Adolescent reports of their perceptions of parental support are related to self-esteem benefits. Parental support is influenced by a host of factors and some are more malleable than others (e.g., parental beliefs vs. child temperament). It is interesting to note that, the degree to which parents trust that children have a natural tendency toward internalization and development strongly influences their capacity to provide support.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- 1) It is recommended that in developing policies for schools, the Ministry of Education, School Administrators, Ministry of Women Affairs, Ministry of Youth Affairs and other stakeholders related to parental support on adolescents be given more serious consideration.
- 2) Educators should pay more attention to the relationship between parental support and adolescents' self-esteem.
- 3) Schools should provide functional counseling services to support the developmental and emotional growth of socially anxious students, considering the fact that they often express fears and feelings of being negatively evaluated during events and in the classroom even when teaching and learning experience is going on and thereby lowering their sense of self-esteem.

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